

1 **AXL and MERTK silencing in breast cancer cells resistance to chemotherapy *in vitro*.**

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7 We report silencing of both *AXL* and *MERTK* in triple negative breast cancer cells in response to exposure
8 to two separate chemotherapeutic agents as a component of the resistance response. These receptors
9 transduced signals for GAS ligands; both *GAS1* and *GAS5* were silenced or significantly repressed.

10 Citations

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